

**YARIM O'QDA BERILGAN SHTURM-LIUVILL CHEGARAVIY MASALASI
HAMDA VEYL-TITCHMARSH FUNKSIYASI VA SPEKTRAL FUNKSIYA
ORASIDAGI BOG'LANISH.**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yarim o'qda berilgan Shturm-Liuvill chegaraviy masalasi hamda Veyl-Titchmarsh funksiyasi va spektral funksiya orasidagi bog'lanish o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yarim o'qda berilgan Shturm - Liuvill chegaraviy masalasi, Veyl-Titchmarsh funksiya, Spektral funksiya, Xos qiymat

Teorema 1. Agar $m(\tau)$ - Veyl nuqtasi yoki veyl doirasiga tegishli bo'lgan biror nuqta bo'lsa, u holda ixtiyoriy $\tau \in C \setminus R$ kompleks son uchun ushbu

$$\begin{cases} -y'' + q(x)y = \tau(y), & (0 \leq x \leq \infty), \\ y'(0) = hy(0), \end{cases}$$

(bu yerda $q(x) \in [0, \infty)$ haqiqiy funksiya, h

ixtiyoriy haqiqiy son va τ kompleks parametr) tenglamaning

$$\varphi(x, \tau) = \theta(x, \tau) + m(\tau)\omega(x, \tau)$$

yechimi $L^2(0, \infty)$ fazoga tegishli bo'ladi hamda quydagi tengsizlikni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\int_0^{\infty} |\varphi(x, \tau)|^2 dx \leq -\frac{\text{Im}m(\tau)}{\text{Im}\tau}$$

Ta'rif 1. $\varphi(x, \tau) = \theta(x, \tau) + m(\tau)\omega(x, \tau)$ yechimga Veyl yechimi, $m(\tau)$ funksiyaga esa Veyl-Titchmarsh funksiyasi deyiladi.

Teorema 2. Agar (a, b) oraliqning chetki nuqtalari $\rho(\lambda)$ spektral funksiyaning uzluksizlik nuqtalaridan iborat bo'lsa, u holda

$$\rho(b) - \rho(a) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_a^b \text{Im}\{m(u + iv)\} du, \quad (2)$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

2-Natija. Spektral funksiyaning xos qiymatdagi sakrash uzunligi Veyl-Titchmarsh funksiyasining shu nuqtadagi chegirmasiga teng:

$$\rho(\lambda_0 + 0) - \rho(\lambda_0 - 0) = \text{res}_{\lambda=\lambda_0} m(\lambda). \quad (2.1)$$

Ushbu

$$-y'' + q(x)y = \lambda y, \quad (0 \leq x \leq b), \quad (3.1)$$

$$y(0) \cos \alpha + y'(0) \sin \alpha = 0, \quad (3.2)$$

chegaraviy masalani qaraymiz. Bu yerda $q(x) \in C[0, \infty)$ haqiqiy funksiya, $\alpha \in R^1$ haqiqiy son.

Agar $\sin \alpha \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda (3.2) chegaraviy shartni

$$y'(0) - hy(0) = 0, \quad h = -ctg \alpha, \quad (3.3)$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. (3.1) formula (3.2) chegaraviy shart bajarilganda keltirib chiqarilgan edi. Shuning uchun

$m(z) = -ctg \alpha + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\rho(\lambda)}{z-\lambda}$, ($\sin \alpha \neq 0$) formuladagi $m(z)$ va $\rho(\lambda)$ funksiyalarni mos ravishda $m_\alpha(z)$ va $\rho_\alpha(\lambda)$ orqali belgilaymiz. Agar (3.1)+(3.3) chegaraviy masalaning spektral funksiyasini $\rho_h(\lambda)$ orqali belgilasak, u holda $\rho_\alpha(\lambda)$ va $\rho_h(\lambda)$ funksiyalar o'zaro quyidagi formulalar bilan bog'langan:

$$\rho_\alpha(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \alpha} \cdot \rho_h(\lambda), \quad (3.4)$$

Shuning uchun (3.1) formulani quyidagicha ko'rinishda yozish mumkin:

$$m_\alpha(z) = -ctg \alpha + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\rho_\alpha(\lambda)}{z-\lambda} = h + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \alpha} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\rho_h(\lambda)}{z-\lambda}. \quad (3.5)$$

Ikkinchi tomondan $\rho_h(\lambda)$ spektral funksiya uchun quyidagi asimptotik formula o'rinli bo'ladi ([81], 397-bet):

$$\rho_h(\lambda) = \frac{2}{\pi} \sqrt{\lambda} - h + \rho_h(-\infty) + \bar{o}(1), \quad (3.6)$$

Spektral funksiyaning bu asimptotik formulasidan va (3.5) formuladan Veyl-Titchmarshning $m_\alpha(z)$ funksiyasi uchun asimptotik formula topishimiz mumkin.

Teorema 3. (3.1) + (3.2) chegaraviy masalaning $m_\alpha(z)$ Veyl-Titchmarsh funksiyasi uchun ushbu $\delta < \arg z < \pi - z$ sohada quyidagi asimptotik formula o'rinli:

$$m_\alpha(z) = -ctg \alpha - \frac{i}{\sqrt{z} \sin^2 \alpha} + \frac{ctg \alpha}{z \sin^2 \alpha} + \bar{o}\left(\frac{1}{z}\right), \quad |z| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (3.7)$$

Bu yerda $\delta > 0$ - biror musbat son.

Misol: Ushbu

$$\begin{cases} -y'' - \frac{2a^2}{ch^2 ax} y = \lambda y, & 0 \leq x < \infty \\ y'(0) - hy(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

Shturm-Liuvill masalasining spektral funksiyasini topamiz.

Ma'lumki masalada berilgan differensial tenglamaning umumiy yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda ifodalanadi:

$$y = C_1 \left(\cos \sqrt{\lambda} x - athax \frac{\sin \sqrt{\lambda} x}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \right) + C_2 (\sqrt{\lambda} \sin \sqrt{\lambda} x + athax \cos \sqrt{\lambda} x).$$

Quyidagi

$$\begin{cases} \theta(x, 0) = 0, \\ \theta'(x, 0) = 1, \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} \varphi(x, 0) = 1, \\ \varphi'(x, 0) = h \end{cases}$$

boshlanich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimlari quyidagicha ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$\theta(x, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda + a^2} (\sqrt{\lambda} \sin \sqrt{\lambda}x + athax \cos \sqrt{\lambda}x),$$

$$\varphi(x, \lambda) = \cos \sqrt{\lambda}x - ath(ax) \frac{\sin \sqrt{\lambda}x}{\sqrt{\lambda}} + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2} (\sqrt{\lambda} \sin \sqrt{\lambda}x + athax \cos \sqrt{\lambda}x),$$

$q(x) \equiv 0$ koeffitsiyent quyidan chegaralanganligi uchun Veylning nuqta holi o'rinli bo'ladi.

Ushbu

$\psi(x, \lambda) = \theta(x, \lambda) + m(\lambda)\varphi(x, \lambda)$ funksiya $L^2(0, \infty)$ fazoga tegishli bo'ladigan qilib, $m(\lambda)$ funksiyani tanlaymiz. Buning uchun quyidagicha ifodalashni bajaramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(x, \lambda) + m(\lambda)\varphi(x, \lambda) &= \frac{1}{\lambda + a^2} (\sqrt{\lambda} \sin \sqrt{\lambda}x + athax \cos \sqrt{\lambda}x) + \\ &+ m(\lambda) \left(\cos \sqrt{\lambda}x - ath(ax) \frac{\sin \sqrt{\lambda}x}{\sqrt{\lambda}} + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2} (\sqrt{\lambda} \sin \sqrt{\lambda}x + athax \cos \sqrt{\lambda}x) \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{athax}{\lambda + a^2} - \frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} + m(\lambda) + \frac{i}{\sqrt{\lambda}} m(\lambda)athax - \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} m(\lambda) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2} m(\lambda)athax \right\} e^{i\sqrt{\lambda}x} + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{athax}{\lambda + a^2} + \frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} + m(\lambda) - \frac{i}{\sqrt{\lambda}} m(\lambda)athax + \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} m(\lambda) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2} m(\lambda)athax \right\} e^{-i\sqrt{\lambda}x}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Kompleks ildizning ushbu

$$\sqrt{u + iv} = \sqrt{\frac{u + \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{2}} + i \sqrt{\frac{-u + \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{2}}, \quad v > 0,$$

shoxchasini tanlash qabul qilinganligi uchun $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$ bo'lganda

$e^{i\sqrt{\lambda}x} \in L^2(0, \infty)$ va $e^{-i\sqrt{\lambda}x} \notin L^2(0, \infty)$,

bo'ladi. Demak, (4) tenglikda ikkinchi qavs ichidagi ifodani nolga tenglaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{athax}{\lambda + a^2} + \frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} + m(\lambda) - \frac{i}{\sqrt{\lambda}}m(\lambda)athax + \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2}m(\lambda) + \\ + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2}m(\lambda)athax = 0, \\ \frac{a}{\lambda + a^2} + \frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} + m(\lambda) - \frac{ia}{\sqrt{\lambda}}m(\lambda) + \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2}m(\lambda) + \frac{h}{\lambda + a^2}m(\lambda)a = 0, \\ \frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} + m(\lambda) + \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2}m(\lambda) = 0 \\ m(\lambda) = \left(-\frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{ih\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2}} = -\frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}}{\lambda + a^2 + ih\sqrt{\lambda}} = \\ = -\frac{i\sqrt{\lambda}(\lambda + a^2) + h\lambda}{(\lambda + a^2)^2 + h^2\lambda}; \end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$\text{Im}\{m(\lambda)\} = -\frac{(\lambda + a^2)\sqrt{\lambda}}{(\lambda + a^2)^2 + h^2\lambda}, \quad \lambda > 0,$$

bo'ladi.

Natija. Ushbu $m(z) = -\text{ctg } \alpha + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\rho(\lambda)}{z-\lambda}$, ($\sin \alpha \neq 0$) tenglikga asosan quyidagi ifodaga kelamiz:

$$\rho'(\lambda) = \begin{cases} \frac{(\lambda + a^2)\sqrt{\lambda}}{\pi(\lambda + a^2)^2 + h^2\lambda}, & \lambda > 0, \\ 0, & \lambda \leq 0, \end{cases}$$

$$\rho(\lambda) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\lambda} \frac{(t + a^2)\sqrt{t}}{(t + a^2)^2 + h^2t} dt, & \lambda > 0, \\ 0, & \lambda \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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